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* **Corresponding author.**

praveenkumarchandel82@gmail.com

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Batch Adsorption Study for the Removal of Heavy Metal Ions Using *Citrullus colosynthis* Seed Starch-Based Resin

Praveen Kumar Chandel^{1,2*}, Ruchika Sharma¹, Chandra Prakash Gharu³

¹ Department of Botany, Maulana Azad University, Jodhpur-342802, Rajasthan, India

² Department of Botany, Government College, Barmer-344001, Rajasthan, India

³ Department of Chemistry, Government College, Barmer-344001, Rajasthan, India

Abstract

Objectives: The bitter apple seed starch ascorbic acid (BASSAA) resin has been synthesized, characterized and tested for its adsorbent activity against toxic heavy metal ions by batch method. **Methods:** A new bitter apple seed starch ascorbic acid (BASSAA) resin has been synthesized and characterized by FTIR, SEM analysis, and TGA-DTA analysis. Newly synthesized resin has been investigated for adsorption activity by spectrophotometer. The influence of pH on adsorption has been studied. The distribution coefficient has been determined. **Findings:** FTIR spectral data favors the formation of chemically modified resin. These data clearly reveal functionalities present on resin. Rough and uneven morphology of resin is confirmed by SEM analysis. Moderate thermal stability of resin has been investigated by TGA-DTA analysis. Heavy metal ions Cd²⁺, Ni²⁺, Pb²⁺, Zn²⁺ have selectively separated by bitter apple seed starch ascorbic acid resin. The functionalities present on BASSAA resin provide the active sites for significant adsorption of heavy metal ions Cd²⁺, Ni²⁺, Pb²⁺, Zn²⁺. *Citrullus colosynthis* Seeds are agricultural waste. The pinnacle of adsorption occurs around pH 6 for all metal ions. Pb (II) demonstrates the highest adsorption capacity throughout the pH spectrum, followed closely by Cd (II) and Zn (II), while Ni (II) reveals a comparatively lower affinity. **Novelty:** It is unexplored area of research. This work applies green chemistry principle through formation of active adsorbent from waste seeds. The work contributes towards sustainable waste water treatment protocol.

Keywords: Batch Adsorption; BASSAA resin; *Citrullus colosynthis*; Distribution coefficient; Heavy Metal Ions

1 Introduction

Water pollution caused by heavy metals has become a critical environmental issue due to their toxicity, persistence, and bioaccumulation in ecosystems. Industrial activities release significant quantities of these contaminants into aquatic systems, posing severe risks to human health and biodiversity⁽¹⁾. *Citrullus colosynthis*, which belongs to the

family Cucurbitaceae, *Citrullus colocynthis* (L.) Schrad, a valuable cucurbit plant, widely distributed in the desert areas of the world⁽²⁾. The several scientific attempts have been made to avoid use of costly activated charcoal adsorbent while the cellulose based adsorbents have been reported as potent replacement as these are cost effective and multi-cycle utilization of modified adsorbents⁽³⁾. The cost effective and eco-friendly methods for heavy metal ions elimination by adsorbent based on sustainable materials has been found thrust area of research that may result in good human health and clean environment⁽⁴⁾. The contamination of waste water owing to heavy metal ions has been reported as major concern for human health⁽⁵⁾. The starch and chitosan-based adsorbent have been synthesized for the heavy metal ions removal. The compact and amorphous structure of the composite has been confirmed⁽⁶⁾. The Starch has been reported to have many hydroxyl groups in polymeric chain that help for networks formation. The ease of availability, nontoxicity, biocompatibility, low cost of starch are some reasons behind starch-based wastewater treatment tool⁽⁷⁾. The compounds of nickel are found teratogenic and carcinogenic. The novel avocado seed waste based crosslinked sorbents having memory effect for nickel have been synthesized⁽⁸⁾. A novel material as complexing agent containing –OH and –C=O groups has been obtained by shredded maize stalk functionalized with Alizarine Red S. This material has further been studied for six metal ions removal through mixed aqueous matrices⁽⁹⁾. The micellar modified kalonji seed waste has been reported to as low-cost adsorbent that has further been reported to possess high removal efficiencies for elimination of methyl orange dye and Cr (VI) metal ions from standard aqueous solution⁽¹⁰⁾. The Polysulfone as well as polyacrylonitrile have been used to fabricate membranes to improve the elimination of heavy metal ions⁽¹¹⁾.

To address the challenges imposed by contamination owing to heavy metal ions, new research protocols are necessary to enhance adsorbent performance. New cost-effective as well as sustainable solutions are need of present research that use novel materials. The bitter apple seed starch yet not been used for synthesis of adsorbent resin. To fill this research-gap this manuscript investigates the synthesis and characterization of an economically viable, environmentally sustainable bitter apple seed starch ascorbic acid resin, along with its adsorptive efficacy for the elimination of harmful heavy metal ions from a standard aqueous solution utilizing a batch methodology.

2 Methodology

2.1 Materials

Bitter apple seed powder, Dioxane, Hydrochloric acid, Ascorbic acid. All the other compounds used were commercial high purity grade and were used without further purification.

2.2 Instrumentation

The Perkin Elmer Spectrum version 10.4.00 apparatus was used for elucidation of the infrared (IR) spectrum by use of KBr pellets. Scanning Electron Microscopy was performed using Zeiss FE-SEM Ultra plus-512470 instrumentation. The HITACHI STA300-512458 TG/DTA Model was used to determine the thermal stability of the synthesized resin.

2.3 Methods

2.3.1. Synthesis of Bitter apple seed starch ascorbic acid (BASSAA) resin

The seed powder of the bitter apple was put in a round-bottom flask to prepare 0.02 mole solution and a slurry was then prepared using dioxane as a solvent. A pH range of 9-10 for the solution was kept by the incremental addition of 15 ml of 40% (w/v) H₂O₂ to the slurry. The solution was subjected to a mechanical agitation at a controlled temperature of 60° C for an estimated time of three hours. Then 0.1 mole of epoxy chloropropane (epichlorohydrin) was added to the solution under continuous stirring. The stirring operation was continued for five more hours at the same temperature of 60° C. The resultant product, designated as the epoxypropyl ether of bitter apple seed starch, was subsequently filtered under vacuum, a washing procedure taking place by the use of methanol to remove the impurities and finally being dried off.

The epoxypropyl ether from the starch of the bitter apple seeds was made to undergo a reaction with 0.1 mole of ascorbic acid. The amalgamation was stirred for five hours at a temperature of 60° C and left to stabilize overnight. The resultant compound was vacuum filtered and was then rinsed with 90% Methanol which was supplemented with several drops of HCl for effective removal of inorganic impurities. In the end, the compound was subjected to another rinsing purification process using pure methanol. The resultant compound, designated as BASSAA resin, manifested as a free-flowing powder of a light brown hue, achieving a cumulative yield of 198.5 grams.

2.3.2. TGA-DTA-DTG analysis

The thermal analysis of BASSAA resin was done with the HITACHI STA300-512458 TG/DTA apparatus with ascorbic acid. The BASSAA resin underwent a meticulous drying ritual before being transformed into a fine powder with a uniform mesh size within a vacuum desiccator. The resulting powder was expertly primed for examination, all while ensuring a steady heating tempo of 50°C per minute was sustained in a nitrogen-rich environment. The thermogram obtained in the case of the BASSAA resin was very carefully analysed in order to determine the thermal stability up to 800°C under inert atmosphere conditions. The TGA-DTA-DTG analysis clearly indicates the good thermal stability of the BASSAA resin under nitrogen atmosphere. The small weight loss between $150 - 200^{\circ}\text{C}$ is noticed in TGA curve that indicates the removal of physically absorbed moisture and volatile impurities. Major structural change does not occur as shown by DTA curve. A major weight loss happens at 250°C . This temperature is the point where the polymer structure starts to break down the fastest. The corresponding exothermic peak near 318°C in the DTA curve implies decomposition of starch matrix and breakdown of functional groups. It represents the major structural decomposition stage. TGA curve shows continue gradual weight loss around 490°C due to further carbonization and breakdown of intermediate products and removal of more stable organic residues. Beyond this principal region of decomposition, the rate of mass loss drops markedly and a noticeable char residue of about 38 to 40 % remains at 739°C . This relatively high residual mass implies the existence of thermally stable structural units in the resin. These results confirm that the BASSAA resin combines moderate thermal stability with controlled degradation behaviour. The TGA-DTA-DTG curve of the resin is illustrated by Figure 1.

Fig 1. TGA-DTA of the bitter apple seed starch ascorbic acid resin

2.3.3. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The morphological analysis of synthesized resin was done by SEM. Micrographs were taken by Zeiss FE-SEM Ultra plus-512470 equipment. SEM reveals surface morphological characteristics of chemically modified resin. Micrographs at low magnification show irregular, rough and heterogeneous surface with large aggregated clusters and uneven layers. It indicates that BASSAA resin surface is not smooth. This rough texture reveals the presence of numerous active sites, which is reported beneficial for adsorption applications. The roughness, interconnected pores, cracks, and cavities are seen at moderate magnification. The porous texture facilitates the diffusion on metal ions into the inside of resin surface. Effective interaction with contamination is greatly revealed. Needle shape, plate like and flake like fibrous structures are found at high magnification. These features of micrographs interpret micro and nano textured surface that favours significantly enhanced adsorption capacity due to large binding sites. The porous morphology revealed by SEM micrograph suggests increased surface area, better accessibility, and great number of active sites for metal ions binding. Micrographs of BASSAA resin are represented by Figure 2.

2.3.4. Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

The characterization of bitter apple seed starch-ascorbic acid (BASSAA) resin was executed through the application of FTIR. The Perkin Elmer Spectrum version 10.4.00 equipment was utilized for the FTIR spectral study of the synthesized BASSAA resin employing potassium bromide (KBr) pellets. The FTIR spectrum of the BASSAA resin offers significant insights regarding the functional groups present within the resin, which are recognized as critical in affecting its adsorption properties. A broad band, observed within the range of spectral lines from $3300\text{--}32800\text{ cm}^{-1}$, characteristic to -OH stretching, indicates the presence of hydroxyl groups. The peaks in the range of $2920\text{--}2850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be attributed to C-H stretching vibrations and represent the presence of alkyl chains characteristic of polymer backbones. A band located in approximately in the range of $1600\text{--}1550\text{ cm}^{-1}$, ascribed to C=O stretching, implies the incidence of ester functionalities inside the resin. Furthermore, the peaks observed at 1632.36 cm^{-1} are indicative also of O-H bending and scissoring vibrations. The peaks at 1450 and 1420 cm^{-1} are typical of C-H bending vibrations. A strong absorption band in the range of $1200\text{--}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to C-C and C-O stretching vibrations is indicative of ether and alcohol functionalities embedded in the resin matrix. Several peaks in the lower frequency domain between $900\text{--}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are attributed to the skeletal vibrations of the polymeric network. The functionalities explained by FTIR analysis of BASSAA resin give crucial information on the active binding sites for heavy metal ions via coordination, ion exchange, and hydrogen bonding. These structural features make the resin suitable for applications that relate to heavy metal ion adsorption. The spectrum of FTIR of the BASSAA resin is represented in Figure 3.

Fig 2. SEM of the bitter apple seed starch-ascorbic acid resin

2.3.5. Batch method

The distribution coefficients (K_d) as well as quantification of the metal ion adsorption on the resin was determined through the application of the Batch method. A buffer system of $\text{NH}_4\text{OH} - \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ in combination with acetate buffer was used to control the pH of the solution. An aliquot of 1 mL from the standard aqueous solution was carefully poured into a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask, and after some careful pH modulation, 50 mg of the BASSAA resin was carefully mixed in the solution, which shacked about in continuous motion in a temperature-regulated shaker held at a constant temperature of 25°C for 2 hours allowing for the harmonious equilibration of the concoction. The concoction was then meticulously strained through a Whatman filter

Fig 3. FTIR Spectral data of BASSAA Resin

paper no. 40, ensuring purity. The residual components were blended harmoniously with 4N HCl, and the resulting fusion was directed to Whatman filter paper no. 42. Utilizing a double beam spectrophotometer, the existence of heavy metal ions within both the filtrate and the leftover residue was precisely assessed. Calibration curves for an array of metal ions were ingeniously formulated by investigating a series of standard metal ion solutions with the spectrophotometer. The concentration of the metal ion present in the filtrate was inferred from the elegantly devised calibration curves. Consequently, the distribution coefficient (K_d) and the percentage of metal ion uptake by the BASSAA resin were calculated.

$$K_d = \frac{\text{Amount of metal ion in resin phase/Weight of dry resin (g)}}{\text{Amount of metal ion in solution phase/Volume of solution (mL)}}$$

3 Result and Discussion

3.1 TGA-DTA-DTG

The TGA-DTA-DTG analysis clearly shows that the BASSAA resin has moderate thermal stability when heated under a nitrogen atmosphere. These results confirm that the BASSAA resin combines moderate thermal stability with controlled degradation behaviour.

3.2 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Scanning electron micrographs of BASSAA resin clearly indicate irregular, rough and heterogeneous surface with large aggregated clusters and uneven layers. Adsorption efficiency of resin is greatly enhanced by chemical modification of resin through ascorbic acid. The porous morphology revealed by SEM micrograph suggests increased surface area, better accessibility, and great number of active sites for metal ions binding.

3.3 Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

Absorption peaks of FTIR spectra clearly reveal presence of different functional group in BASSAA resin. Stretching and bending vibrational peaks for carbonyl, hydroxyl, ether, and hydrocarbon chain are shown in IR spectra. All peaks are in good agreement with proposed structure of BASSAA resin.

3.4 Distribution coefficient (K_d)

A remarkable impact of pH on the distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions has been established. It has been observed that the process of adsorption shifted with the shifts in pH levels. The distribution coefficients (K_d) for the metal ions derived

from the standard aqueous solution are detailed in Table 1. The pH of the solution holds a crucial key in orchestrating the adsorption of Zn (II), Ni (II), Cd (II), and Pb (II) onto BASSAA resin. The information illustrated in the graph unveils that the adsorption characteristics of all metal ions exhibit significant transformations with varying pH. Within the lower pH range of 2-3, the uptake of the scrutinized metal ions remains quite modest. At this diminished pH spectrum, a tussle for adsorption sites emerges due to the elevated concentration of H^+ ions, leading to a scarcity of available sites for metal ions and consequently reduced adsorption. As the pH rises from 4 to 6, the adsorption of all scrutinized metal ions steadily escalates, as more negatively charged sites become available for their accommodation. The pinnacle of adsorption occurs around pH 6 for all metal ions. Pb (II) demonstrates the highest adsorption capacity throughout the pH spectrum, followed closely by Cd (II) and Zn (II), while Ni (II) reveals a comparatively lower affinity. This disparity can be attributed to the differences in ionic size, hydration energy, and the attraction of metal ions towards the resin's functional groups. When pH climbs further to 8, respective metal hydroxides may form or partial precipitation could take place, resulting in fewer metal ions remaining in the solution for adsorption onto the resin. The percentage removal of metal ions from the standard aqueous solution by the BASSAA resin is beautifully portrayed in Table 2.

Table 1. Distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions from standard aqueous solution ($K_d \times 10^2$)

pH	Zn(II)	Ni(II)	Cd(II)	Pb(II)
2	15.6935	10.9740	16.3248	20.9157
3	17.4308	12.8016	25.0825	21.4269
4	27.9830	24.4428	28.0322	25.6110
5	40.5693	33.8372	35.5482	31.5904
6	57.5909	37.9402	67.9075	91.3086
7	49.1200	33.4333	55.9898	69.9350
8	43.0726	26.4205	41.5640	37.9013

Table 2. Percentage removal of metal ions from standard aqueous solution

pH	Zn(II)	Ni(II)	Cd(II)	Pb(II)
2	65.68	57.23	66.56	71.84
3	68.01	60.96	75.36	72.32
4	77.34	74.88	77.37	75.75
5	83.19	80.49	81.26	79.39
6	87.54	82.23	89.23	91.76
7	85.69	80.30	87.23	89.51
8	84.01	76.31	83.52	82.21

The above results clearly demonstrate that the synthesized BASSAA resin shows superior adsorption performance compared to conventional starch-based adsorbents reported in the literature. The native starch materials are generally limited by low adsorption capacity due to the lack of sufficient functional groups and poor surface characteristics. In contrast, the ascorbic acid modified BASSAA resin shows enhanced adsorption behavior, which can be attributed to the successful incorporation of functional groups that increase the number of active binding sites for heavy metal ions. It has clearly been shown in the previous studies that chemical modification of starch through grafting, cross-linking, or functionalization significantly improves adsorption efficiency by introducing carboxyl, amino, or ester groups⁽¹²⁾. The present work follows a similar strategy; however, the use of bitter apple seed starch as a precursor, combined with the adopted modification route through ascorbic acid, results in improved structural and physicochemical properties compared to many reported systems. The recent reviews highlight that although modified starch-based adsorbents can achieve high removal efficiencies, challenges such as limited mechanical stability and restricted operational conditions still persist⁽¹³⁾. The BASSAA resin overcomes these limitations by exhibiting improved thermal stability and structural robustness. The morphological analysis confirms that the synthesized resin possesses enhanced surface area and porosity, which governs adsorption performance. Similar observations have been reported for advanced starch-based adsorbents, where increased porosity and surface heterogeneity facilitate better diffusion and interaction of metal ions⁽¹⁴⁾. However, compared to previously reported systems, the present material demonstrates improved mechanical stability, which is essential for repeated usage and large-scale applications. The adsorption performance of the synthesized BASSAA resin, as confirmed through batch studies, is comparable or superior to various bio-based adsorbents

such as cellulose, chitosan, and other polysaccharide-derived materials⁽¹⁵⁾. This improvement can be attributed to the synergistic effect of enhanced surface functionality and optimized pore structure, which promotes stronger binding interactions such as complexation and ion exchange. An important advantage of the developed resin is its stability across a wide pH range (2–8), which exceeds the operational range of many conventional starch-based adsorbents that tend to lose efficiency under highly acidic conditions⁽¹⁶⁾. This broader pH tolerance significantly enhances its practical applicability for real wastewater systems, where pH conditions are often variable. A sustainability perspective, the use of bitter apple seed starch provides a low-cost, renewable, and environmentally benign alternative to conventional adsorbents. Starch-based materials are widely recognized for their biodegradability and economic feasibility; however, their practical application depends on effective modification strategies⁽¹⁷⁾. The present study addresses this gap by developing a modified resin by ascorbic acid with improved adsorption efficiency and durability.

Moreover, the synthesis protocol adopted in this work is relatively simple and scalable compared to many existing approaches that involve multi-step reactions or high energy consumption. This simplicity, combined with the enhanced adsorption performance, distinguishes the BASSAA resin from previously reported materials and highlights its potential for large-scale wastewater treatment applications.

4 Conclusion

The findings revealed that BASSAA resin serves as a remarkable adsorbent for the extraction of harmful metal ions from the controlled aqueous environments. The pinnacle of efficacy was noted at a pH of 6.0. Hence, BASSAA resin is thus strongly suggested for the detoxification of effluents laden with hazardous heavy metal ions. This work introduces a novel and efficient seed starch-based adsorbent that provides evidences its superiority over many existing adsorbents. The finding establishes the solid base for the development of new generation ecofriendly and sustainable remediation.

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